

INFLUENCE OF POST-COVID-19 STRATEGIC TEACHING-LEARNING STYLE ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG BASIC SCIENCE STUDENTS IN MALUMFASHI EDUCATIONAL ZONE, KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study reports the findings of the research conducted on the Influence of Post-COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style on Academic Performance among Basic Science Students in Malumfashi Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. The direction of the study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. It adopted descriptive survey of ex-post facto design. The population of the study consisted of 1,129 JSS 2 Basic Science Students in ten Public Junior Secondary Schools under Malumfashi Zonal Education Quality Assurance (MZEQA) in 2019/2020 academic session. Using stratified random sampling technique, 135 students from three co-educational schools in the study area were engaged. Second Term 2018/2019 Students' performances in Basic Science and Second Term 2019/2020 Students' performance in Basic Science were obtained for the study. The two research questions were answered using mean and standard deviations while null hypotheses one and two were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Paired z-test and Independent sample z-test respectively. The findings of the study revealed that there is significant difference between the performance of Basic science students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 teaching-learning Strategy. The findings also revealed that there was no significance difference in the academic achievement scores of male and female Basic Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic teaching-learning Style. It was recommended that, alternative strategic teaching-learning styles should be adopted other than the conventional ones been adopted so as to prevent the negative influence of the strategies on academic achievement of the students. Also, government should try strategies like blended teaching-learning among other.

Keyword: Post-COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style, Academic Performance, Basic Science Students

Introduction

Pandemic or crisis have become characteristics of each century. For instance; World War II characterized the 20th Century and Coronavirus Disease-2019 alias COVID-19 characterized the 21st Century. In each of those eras affected, world's economy, education and mode of human interaction and other aspect of human endeavor were disturbed. Presently, the shadow of the 21st century's pandemic (COVID-19) has not completely been casted-out. Coronavirus disease is a novel respiratory disease, a zoonotic pneumonia-like that evolved toward the end of the year 2019. World Health Organisation (WHO) toll the alarming bell noting the outbreak of a disease firstly detected in Wuhan City of Hubei Province in China on 30th December 2019 (WHO, 2020). A month later, the organization declared the disease as international public health emergency on 30th January 2020 as well as global pandemic on 11th March 2020 (WHO, 2020; Cucinotta & Vanelli, 2020). The first case of the virus recorded in Africa

was in Egypt. It was characterized with fast spreading ability ranging from animals to humans and human to human. As a communicable disease (contagious) with rapid potent of spreading, COVID-19 lingers buffing more than its effects.

Education is one of the most affected organ during the COVID-19 especially in Nigeria. Schools at all levels were vacated and closed to avoid the spread of the disease. Global communities experienced series of lockdown with minimal interactions enforced by taskforces (Li, et al., 2020). Access to any learning academies and centers were banned and closed. It was reported that, around 600 million students at different level of learning were affected worldwide due to the closure of the schools (Goyal, 2020) which was extended to the population of about 1.7 billion students in 192 countries of the 7 continents of the world (UNESCO, 2020). In the meantime, the condition last longer than expected (almost 8 months). The students, pupils and perhaps teachers were hopelessly waiting for positive announcements by the government about schools reopening. Undeniably, the closure of various learning institutions nationally, internationally and locally brought about multiple impact to the Nigerian education system (most of which are negative).

As an alternative standby solution to the existing problem, many developed and some of the developing countries adopted an online means teaching and learning so as to reduce the disruption of the planned semesters and terms (Abidah, et al., 2020). On the other hand, other developmentally retarded nations were found to be at disadvantage side as their schools were left with no option other than to remain closed (Nigeria inclusive). This negative storm of the general school closure generates a tremendous impact on the academic stand of the Nigerian students both in teaching-learning process and assessments (UNESCO, 2020).

In Nigeria, the vacation lasted for over six months after which the government, stakeholders, communities and civic societies in collaboration with the Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH) and Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) taskforce on COVID-19 resolve and evaluate the situation as ready for schools to re-opened. Before schools and learning centers reopen in Katsina state, Ministry of Education Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC), State Universal Basic Education Board Katsina (SUBEB) on training for the headmasters and principals for secondary schools on COVID-19 Pandemic in Preparation for School re-opening in the State prompt that, the federal and state ministry of education should decide when to reopen schools after due consultations with the Presidential Taskforce (PTF) on COVID-19 and other critical stakeholders, including parent/guardians, teachers' unions, communities, education services providers, PTAs and School Based Management Committees (SBMCs) (UBEC, SUBEB, SMOH KT & NCDC 2020).

Henceforth, the reopening of schools was agreed under the guidance of some protocols which was believed to minimize further spread of the disease among the students. This resulted to what in this study termed as "Post-COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style". The style is composed of set of

guidelines and or protocols and alternative safe practices mandated to be met in the classrooms and schools at large. The guidelines are as follows;

- In schools and other learning facilities, learners should be supported to stay two meter (2m) apart. This is achieved through:
- *Outdoor Learning*: this can limit transmission and also allows for safe distancing between learners and teachers.
- *Staggered Attendance*: learners may arrive and depart at different times to avoid overcrowding; schools may reopen gradually (e.g. starting with particular grade levels).
- *Alternate Attendance*: schools may alternate attendance days per week, with learners at the secondary level (or equivalent) and above having fewer in-person classes, since these learners can manage independent learning (e.g. junior secondary school learners attend on Tuesdays and Thursdays & senior school learners on Mondays, Wednesdays and Fridays).
- *Decreased Interaction*: learners may remain in one location with teachers coming to them.
- *Flexible Schedule*: lessons may be structured in a way that reduces the need for learners and staff to move.
- *Platooning*: classes may be divided into morning and afternoon shifts between the different areas of the premises.
- *Creative Delivery*: lessons may be delivered more holistically to take into account various learning environments for in-person learning (indoor, outdoor) and various media for distance learning (Printed Materials, online, TV, and Radio).
- *Cough Etiquette*: Teachers and students should cover their mouth and nose with protectives (cloth mask, medical mask or face shield).
- *Temperature Monitoring*: teachers' and students' body temperature should be monitored using distant measuring instrument (IR Thermometer) periodically during school hours to ensure normal body temperature and to identify and report anybody with elevated body temperature for further checkup (UBEC, SUBEB, SMOH KT & NCDC, 2020).

At classroom level, academic performance is the most important tool to determine success or otherwise of teaching and learning at a time. Students' academic achievement is defined by Kpolovie, Joe and Okoto (2014) as the manifest of ability of the students to communicate his/her learned knowledge either orally or in written form even in an examination condition. It indicates the outcome of teaching by the teacher and learning by the student. However, inconclusive multi-variables were found to affect academic achievements of students at a time. Factors like interest in learning, study habit, attribution, learning condition, stress, self-efficacy, intelligence, and motivation. Thus, manipulating one or more of these variables as dependent on academic achievement of student, the achievement could be maintained, enhanced or declined (Kpolovie, Joe and Okoto, 2014). In the study conducted by Al-zoubi & Bani-Younes (2015) also identified poor relationship between teachers and students in the teaching-

learning process and learning environmental factors as determinants of students' academic achievement. Ariffin et al. (2017) focused on the role of suitable classroom atmosphere as a function of their academic achievement. Other researchers reported several psychological implications that affected the students as a result of the social impact generated by COVID-19 at various levels ranging from mental traumas (Chandasiri, 2020; Meo et al., 2020), emotional depression, anxiety and frustration (Brooks, et al., 2020) and worries (Cao, et al., 2020). Thus, emotion, anxiety, frustration, worries and other psychological and behavioral factors are indices that can determine students' attitude toward learning which in turn affect students' performance.

So far, Oyiloye (2020) conducted a study on possible impact of COVID-19 on Senior Secondary School students' performance in Science Education in Nigeria. The findings indicate the possibility of further drop of the pass rate percentage due to early closure of schools and disruption of schools' calendar. Nobrega, et al. (2020) investigate the effect of face mask wearing or face shield by young students on their academic performance and it was found to affect the performance of students negatively compared to those learn without face-mask or face shield. The study conducted by Jada, Giginyu and Mutah (2021) revealed that, COVID-19 pandemic has negative impact on students' academic performance of federal university Dutse, Jigawa State, Nigeria. The study conducted by Aji (2021) revealed that, there was a significant difference in mean scores of students before and during COVID-19 in senior secondary school Chemistry. It is against this background argument that this study intends to objectively determine the Influence of Post-COVID-19 Strategic Learning Style on students' Performance in Basic Science.

Statement of the Problem

The alterations made on teaching-learning conditions mandated for learning in Nigerian (Katsina in particular) secondary schools after the first wave of COVID-19 pandemic to be disturbed. In this study, these alterations were assumed to affect the students' academic performance in one way or the other. For instance, outdoor learning, staggered attendance, alternate attendance aimed at decreasing students-students interaction and even teacher-students interaction at classroom and schools at large is believed to disturb among others mental health of the young students (Deighton et al., 2019). Also, some topics in science require activity methods in form of collaborative and cooperative strategies which was totally prevented as a way to contained COVID-19. Wearing of face mask also was found to affect students' performance in the sense that, during teaching learning process, children were unable to obtain visual cues, hiding the teachers' face and not allowing the lip reading whereas, the voice of the teacher is diminished and maybe distorted. Other protocols like platooning and flexible schedule for teachers are presumed to be added stress to both students and teachers. Report of the elevation of temperature monitored periodically of a student or teacher in the school may create a traumatic situation in the school which ipso facto affect students' concentration, fear of school, anxiety and emotional disturbance. Hence, students' performance is at risk. To examine the influence of these factors, this study set to

determine the influence of Post-COVID-19 Strategic Learning Style on students' performance in Basic Science.

Research Questions

The study addressed the following research questions:

1. What is the mean difference in academic achievement scores of Basic Science students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style?
2. Is there any difference in the academic achievement scores of male and female Basic Science Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style?

Research Hypotheses

The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Basic science students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style.
2. There is no statistical significance difference in the academic achievement scores of male and female Basic Science Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style.

Methodology

The research was a descriptive survey of ex-post facto design. It involves no treatment and manipulation of independent variable. It also involves the collection of data from records. The main aim will be to observe the effects of what has already occurred [i.e. the achievement scores of students before (preceding term) and after (proceeding term) being taught with COVID-19 Teaching-Learning Strategy].

The population of this study will have comprised of all Junior secondary schools in Malumfashi Local Government Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA) Katsina State who are offering Basic Science as a Subject. This is because, the Post-COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning style was integrally employed across the Secondary Schools in the State to contain the spread of the virus in schools. According to the Malumfashi Local Government Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA) staff return of the month of February 2021 of 2019/2020 academic session, there are Ten (10) public Junior secondary schools of 2019/2020 Session under its coordination. The schools comprise of total One Thousand One Hundred and Twenty-Nine (1,129) JSS 2 Basic Science Students with average age of 13 years.

For this study, three (3) co-educational secondary schools were selected using stratified random sampling technique out of targeted population in order to cater for gender variable. The students in the sampled schools comprised of One Hundred and Thirty-Five Basic Science Students (135) of which

Eighty-Four student (84) are males and Fifty-one (51) females. For the purpose of data collection, the researcher made personal contact with all the selected schools and collected the following records; Second Term 2018/2019 Students' performance in Basic Science and Second Term 2019/2020 Students' performance in Basic Science. The two research questions one and two were answered using mean and standard deviations whereas null hypotheses one and two were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Paired z-test and Independent sample z-test respectively.

Presentation of Results

Question 1: What is the Mean Difference in Academic Achievement Scores of Science Students Before and After being Exposed to COVID-19 Teaching-Learning Strategy?

Table 1: Means and standard deviations of students' scores before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Teaching-Learning Strategy

Scores of Students	N	Mean and Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Mean difference
Before	135	63.41± 21.58	1.858	18.82
After	135	44.59±20.35	1.751	

Table 1 show the computation of scores of the students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Teaching-Learning Strategy. The results show that mean performance of students before the pandemic was 63.41 while, after being exposed to Covid-19 teaching-learning Strategy, the mean performance of the students was 44.59. This indicate that there exists mean difference between the performance of Basic science students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 teaching-learning Strategy. However, the standard deviation before after are 21.58 and 20.35 respectively which show wider spread of scores away from the means. The mean difference is 18.82 in favour of the 'Before'.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Basic science students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style.

Table 2: Analysis of paired z-test of the Performance of Basic Science Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style

Students' Scores	N	Mean and Std. Deviation	df	z-cal	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Before	135	63.41± 21.58	134	7.418	.000	Rejected
After	135	44.59±20.35				

From Table 2 shows the analysis of paired z-test statistics shows that significant difference exists in the mean performance of Basic Science Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style. This is because, the p-value is .000 which is less than α value of $p \leq$

.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis one is hereby rejected. Meanwhile, there was significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Basic science students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Teaching-Learning Strategy.

Research Question Two: Is there any difference in the academic achievement scores of male and female Basic Science Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style?

Table 3: Means and Standard Deviations of Male and Female Basic Science Students' Scores before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Teaching-Learning Strategy

Students' Scores		N	Mean and Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Mean Difference
Before	Males	84	60.76 ± 20.62	2.25	7
	Females	51	67.76 ± 22.63	3.17	
After	Males	84	43.38 ± 21.58	2.36	3.21
	Females	51	46.59 ± 18.16	2.55	

Table 3 shows that, before COVID-19 pandemic, the mean performance of male Basic Science students is 60.76 and that of females is 57.76. While, after being exposed to COVID-19 teaching-learning strategy, the mean performance of males is 43.38 and that of females is 46.59. This indicate a mild difference within the groups with mean difference of 7 before and 3.21 after being exposed to COVID-19 teaching-learning Strategy. However, with the standard deviations of 20.62 and 22.63 for males and females respectively, before the pandemic and 21.58 and 18.16 for males and females respectively shows that both scores are dispersed widely away from their respective means.

Ho2: There is no statistical significance difference in the academic achievement scores of male and female Basic Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style.

Table 4: Independent Sample z-test Analysis of Male Basic Science Students Before and After Being Exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style

Students' Scores		N	Mean and Std. Deviation	df	z-cal	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Before	Males	84	60.76 ± 20.62	133	-1.844	.067	Accepted
	Females	51	67.76 ± 22.63				
After	Males	84	43.38 ± 21.58	133	-.887	.376	Accepted
	Females	51	46.59 ± 18.16				

Table 4 presented an Independent sample z-test analysis which shows that there was insignificant difference in the performance of male and female Basic Science students before and after being exposed

to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style. This is because, the p-value before is 0.067 which is slightly greater than α value of $p \leq .05$ level of significance. So also, the p-value after is 0.376 which is greater than α value of $p \leq .05$ level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis two is hereby accepted. Meanwhile, there is no statistical significance difference in the academic achievement scores of male and female Basic Science Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Teaching-Learning Strategy.

Summary of the Major Findings

1. Significant difference exists in the mean performance of Basic Science Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style.
2. There was insignificant difference in the performance of male and female Basic Science students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of this study disclosed that there was significant difference in the mean performance of Basic Science Students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style. This confirms the difference manifested between the performance mean scores of students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style in favour of Before COVID-19 pandemic. This could be attributed to the disturbances in the Teaching-Learning the students encountered to contain the spread of COVID-19. Such instabilities include outdoor learning, staggered attendance, alternate attendance, platooning, flexible schedule, temperature monitoring and wearing of face-mask or face shield during teaching and learning. This finding is in concordance with the findings of Aji (2021); Oyiloye (2020); Jada, et al. (2021) who in their separate studies found out that, COVID-19 session coupled with its precaution routes have negatively impacted students' performance at different levels of education. The findings of this study also revealed that insignificant difference exists in the performance of male and female Basic Science students before and after being exposed to COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style. This finding indicates that the influence is not gender related. In other words, it affects students irrespective of gender difference. This could be associated with fact that those alterations made in the classroom teaching-learning is collective and mandated to all students regardless of gender. Accordingly, both boys and girls must wear face-mask and must also sit far apart from each other as recommended.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusion is made, the spread of COVID-19 forced all schools under Malumfashi Zonal Education Quality Assurance to be closed for over half a year. Hence, containment measures were promulgated to all institution, schools inclusive, among which the normal teaching-learning conditions was altered/disturbed in form of outdoor learning, staggered

attendance, alternate attendance, platooning, flexible schedule, temperature monitoring and wearing of face-mask or face shield. These are the composite of 'Post-COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style'. Literature shows that disturbance or alteration of normal atmosphere may have an impact on academic performance of students. As such, this study set to determine the influential effect (if any) of Post-COVID-19 Strategic Teaching-Learning Style on academic performance of students in Basic Science. The finding of this study revealed that the performance of students decreased during COVID-19 containment compared to their performance before COVID-19 irrespective gender difference.

Recommendations

- i. Teaching strategies such as Simulation Method, Blended Learning, Distance Learning should be adopted by teachers in order to teach the students from their homes. Simulation Method will also assist in teaching those lesson content that require practical activities.
- ii. Educational Stakeholder (SUBEB and UBEC) should provide directives for coverage of the missing content during lockdown. This will help to minimize future detrimental performance of the students.
- iii. Parent and guidance should endeavour to help their children at home through drilling and re-teaching. This will help them to understand the misperceived aspects taught at school.
- iv. In the meantime, teachers at classroom should adopt speaking loudly, repeating instruction, rephrasing and over-emphasizing their statements during teaching session in classroom. This will help the students get what the teacher is trying to explain correctly.
- v. In the meantime, also, students should be encouraged to listen very well and observe their teacher very carefully during learning session. This will help them get what the teacher is saying as they wear face-mask. It will also help the students read teacher's non-verbal cues and other facial expressions.

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